

European Cloud for Heritage Open Science

Milestone MS31

Status Report on the Development of the ECHOES Curriculum

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1. Overview

This milestone confirms the current status of the development of the ECHOES Curriculum, which constitutes a key component of the project’s capacity-building strategy for the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH) (see below).

The curriculum is being developed within Work Package 5 (Capacity Building and Training) and aims to provide structured training resources enabling cultural heritage professionals, researchers, and other stakeholders to understand and adopt the tools, services, and workflows offered by the Cultural Heritage Cloud.

The milestone confirms that the conceptual framework, development workflows, and first training resources are progressing in line with the WP5 roadmap as outlined in the project’s strategic documents (see below).

2. Strategic Framework

The development of the ECHOES Curriculum builds on the strategic foundations established in earlier WP5 deliverables:

- **D5.1 – Principles for Capacity Building.** Defines the core principles guiding capacity-building activities within ECHOES, including inclusivity, accessibility, sustainability, interdisciplinarity, multilingualism, and alignment with Open Science and FAIR practices. These principles informed the pedagogical and organisational choices made during the development of the first foundational course, particularly the emphasis on accessible language, glossary-supported terminology, progressive learning pathways, and the use of practical examples intended for diverse cultural heritage communities, including non-specialist users. See <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17513834>.
- **D5.3 – Strategy and Roadmap for Capacity Building, Training and Knowledge Transfer.** Establishes the strategic direction for the development of the ECHOES Curriculum by defining target communities, training typologies, curricular priorities, and the broader role of training within the ECCCH ecosystem. It also positions the curriculum as a structured and evolving framework supporting the adoption of ECCCH services, workflows, and Vertical Applications. The design of the introductory course as a foundational entry point into the wider curriculum directly follows the roadmap and training architecture outlined in D5.3. See <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17747265>.

These two documents provide the conceptual and operational basis for the design and implementation of training activities within the project.

3. Operational framework for training resources development

In parallel with the development of the first curriculum resources, the **D5.2 ECHOES Model Workflow for Developing Training Resources (D5.2)** has also been finalised. This deliverable operationalises the strategic principles and curricular directions established in D5.1 and D5.3 by defining a structured framework for the development, publication, integration, evaluation, and long-term maintenance of ECHOES training resources.

- roles and responsibilities for training development,
- structured stages for course production,
- quality assurance procedures,
- mechanisms for the maintenance and evolution of training resources over time, and
- and alignment with the broader ECHOES Integration Strategy and Roadmap.

In this sense, D5.2 provides the operational basis for the sustainable expansion of the ECHOES Curriculum across work packages, Vertical Applications, sister projects, and Cascading Grants activities.

The development and publication of the introductory ECCCH course also served as an initial practical application and validation context for several components of the workflow, including curricular structuring, review procedures, glossary integration, user testing, and iterative revision practices.

The D5.2 deliverable shares the same submission deadline as this milestone (M24).

4. Current Implementation Status

The first foundational training resource of the curriculum “Introduction to the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage” has been finalised and published on [DARIAH-Campus](#).

The course was designed as the foundational entry point into the broader ECHOES Curriculum and as an onboarding resource for future users of the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage, with clearly defined learning goals, learning objectives, target audiences, intended impact and modular learning units.

4.1 Learning goals

The Cultural Heritage Cloud (ECCCH) is a major European initiative designed to provide heritage professionals and researchers with access to data and advanced digital tools. The goal of this course is to build learners’ foundational understanding of the key concepts and technologies necessary to engage with the cloud, demonstrate some of its practical tools and applications, and inspire their further exploration of digital transformation in the heritage and research domains.

4.2 Learning objectives

Upon completion of this course, learners will be able to:

- understand key concepts such as collaborative cloud, digital commons, digital twins, and vertical applications
- grasp the relevance of the Cloud for cultural heritage and research work
- identify the main players, applications, and tools within the Cloud
- recognize pathways for continued learning and next steps for engaging with the Cloud

4.3 Target audiences

- Cultural heritage professionals
- Researchers and students in the arts and humanities
- ECHOES Cascading Grants applicants and recipients
- Policymakers

4.4 Intended impact

This course lowers the entry barrier to the emerging European Collaborative Cultural Heritage Cloud by providing a clear, accessible introduction to its concepts, services, and participation pathways. It addresses the practical need for non-technical orientation to a complex and evolving infrastructure, while contributing to the strategic goal of building capacity across the cultural heritage sector. By preparing users to understand, follow, and eventually engage with the Cloud, it supports broader and more informed participation in a connected, interoperable, and community-driven digital ecosystem.

4.5 Requirements

No prior experience with cloud technologies or advanced digital tools is assumed. Basic digital literacy and curiosity about collaborative digital practices in cultural heritage will help users take full advantage of this course.

4.6 Table of Contents

The course is organised into six units that progressively introduce the conceptual foundations, collaborative principles, and practical applications of the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage. Combining accessible explanations with concrete cultural heritage examples and workflow-oriented scenarios, the course is designed to support learners with little or no prior technical knowledge. The course is structured modularly, allowing individual units to be consulted and reused independently of each other where appropriate.

Unit	Title	Focus
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1	Introduction to the Cloud	Introduction to the ECCCH and the concept of the Collaborative Cloud
2	Key Concepts and Terminology	Core concepts including interoperability, data models, digital ecosystems, and digital twins
3	Collaboration in the Cloud	Human-to-human, human-to-machine, and institutional collaboration
4	Open Science and FAIR	FAIR principles and responsible reuse of cultural heritage data
5	How the Cloud Works	Practical workflows, tools, and interactions within the ECCCH ecosystem
6	Continuing the Journey	Further learning pathways and future engagement opportunities

4.7 The platform

DARIAH-Campus is the training and discovery platform of the Digital Research Infrastructure for Arts and Humanities (DARIAH). It supports the dissemination and long-term accessibility of open educational resources for the arts, humanities and related fields. Training materials are openly accessible and published under a Creative Commons licence, facilitating reuse and adaptation by other projects, institutions, and training providers. In line with the broader principles of Open Science and FAIR-oriented knowledge sharing promoted within ECHOES, the publication through DARIAH-Campus also supports discoverability, persistent referencing, and the integration of training resources within a wider European research infrastructure ecosystem. Resources hosted on DARIAH-Campus are subject to the [DARIAH-Campus Reuse Charter](#) and its six core principles of Reciprocity, Interoperability, Citability, Openness, Stewardship and Trustworthiness, which are also reflected in the design and the daily operations of the platform.

4.8 Testing

Prior to release, the course underwent a formative user-review process involving eight individual reviewers with different levels of familiarity with the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage and related digital heritage concepts. The review process followed a text-first and user-centred approach intended to evaluate clarity, accessibility, conceptual progression, and overall usability before the integration of the final visual and multimedia components.

Reviewers were asked to provide qualitative feedback directly within the draft course materials, focusing in particular on:

- passages that were unclear or difficult to understand,
- concepts requiring additional explanation,

- terminology that might not be familiar to non-specialist audiences,
- and areas where the structure, framing, or presentation could be improved.

In addition, reviewers responded to a short set of open-ended reflective questions concerning the overall learning experience, the clarity of the conceptual framework, the achievement of learning objectives, and potential gaps or missing perspectives.

The methodological approach adopted for the review process reflects the broader pedagogical principles established in D5.1 and D5.3, particularly the emphasis on accessibility, inclusivity, progressive learning pathways, and usability for diverse cultural heritage communities with varying levels of technical expertise.

Reviewer feedback was subsequently integrated into a revised version of the course. Responses were overall positive regarding the course’s accessibility, pedagogical design, and conceptual framing. In particular, reviewers highlighted the use of accessible language, glossary-supported terminology, practical examples, and supplementary readings as important strengths of the course. The review process also contributed to the identification of additional terminology and concepts that informed the continued expansion of the ECHOES glossary, now published through: https://vocabs.ilc4clarin.ilc.cnr.it/skosmos/echoes_glossary/en/.

This introductory module will serve as the entry point for the ECHOES curriculum, enabling users to progressively engage with more specialised training resources that will be developed later in the project. As part of the evolving ECHOES training ecosystem, the course will continue to be evaluated and refined through user feedback, curricular updates, and the ongoing expansion of ECCCH services, tools, and workflows.

5. Next steps

Following the publication of the introductory course, the next phase of curriculum development will focus both on expanding the portfolio of training resources and on supporting the learning journeys of the different user communities through progressively adapted training pathways and specialised educational materials.

Planned activities include:

- application-specific training modules for the three Vertical Applications developed within the project:
 - OCRA – Online Conservation Restoration Annotator
 - VTL – Virtual Transcription Laboratory
 - CIT – Collection Ingestion Tool
- the application of the training workflow with other work packages, sister projects, and especially Cascading Grants recipients, in order to support the development of specialised courses and training resources addressing additional thematic, methodological, and technical areas relevant to the ECCCH ecosystem. In particular, these activities are intended to facilitate the integration of Cascading Grants outcomes into the broader ECHOES Curriculum, ensuring that externally developed resources,

datasets, and workflows can become discoverable, reusable, and pedagogically integrated within the Collaborative Cloud environment

Within the project, an agreement is already in place with T7.4.4 to test the workflow through the production of a course that will assist cultural heritage institutions and individuals in adding and enriching semantic descriptions of their data collections. The development of this course will provide a concrete cross-work-package validation scenario for the ECHOES training workflow by involving collaborators who were not directly engaged in WP5 training activities. In parallel, connections with WP3 and the ECHOES Integration Task Force (EITF) will support the coordination of capacity-building activities with sister projects and contribute to the broader integration of externally developed training resources within the evolving ECHOES Curriculum.

These activities will feed into the **D5.4 ECHOES Curriculum Report**, which will present the consolidated curriculum architecture and training portfolio.

6. Conclusion

The development of the ECHOES curriculum is progressing according to the WP5 roadmap and the project timeline.

The strategic framework is established, the operational workflow has been finalised, and the first foundational course published. These elements collectively ensure that the full curriculum will be delivered by the end of the project as planned and will provide a sustainable training framework for future users of the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage.

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